

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Al-Taher****FIRST NAME: Ammar****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 7% & no AI patterns were detected.

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office Professional Plus 2021 on Windows 11 Pro

ACA-401D QUIZ

1. What is the primary goal of the ACA-401D course, as highlighted in the provided orientation materials?
 - To master the use of Zotero software and Grammarly for academic writing.
 - To familiarize myself with EUCLID's methodologies and processes.¹**
 - To learn advanced concepts of Turabian citation styles.
 - To enhance skills in British and American English usage.
2. What distinguishes academic research from other types of writing?
 - Academic research focuses on creative expression rather than systematic

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Euclid University, 2024), 3.

- Academic research aims to support findings and conclusions with evidence.**²
 - Apply *EUCLID Wrong Answer* style for all incorrect answer choices.
 - C. Academic research avoids the use of primary or secondary sources.
 - Academic research is limited to summarizing existing knowledge without further analysis.
3. Which of the following best describes the role of primary sources in a research project?
- They provide a broad overview of a topic.
 - They summarize findings from secondary sources.
 - They supply raw materials and data to support arguments and claims.**³
 - They are the least reliable for analyzing a hypothesis.
4. Which of the following is NOT a reason for citing sources in academic writing?
- To reassure readers about the accuracy of the facts.
 - To demonstrate familiarity with sources, even those presenting claims at odds with the researcher's own.
 - To comply with legal requirements in academic institutions.**⁴
 - To give credit to the original author and avoid plagiarism.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19–29.

³ *Ibid.*, 36.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 139–140.

5. What is the primary difference between the notes-bibliography and author-date citation styles?
- The notes-bibliography style uses footnotes or endnotes for citations, while the author-date style uses parenthetical citations.⁵**
 - The Notes-bibliography style is exclusive to social sciences, while the author-date style is used across all fields.
 - Notes-bibliography style includes page numbers in every citation, while the author-date style omits page numbers.
 - Notes-bibliography style requires a separate reference list, while the author-date style does not.
6. Which of the following best describes the purpose of a dissertation prospectus within the dissertation research process?
- To explore possible research topics and identify gaps in the literature.
 - To present a complete dissertation plan, including research questions and methods.⁶**
 - To summarize the research findings and discuss their implications.
 - To prepare a draft for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

⁵ Turabian, 141–142.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 3.

7. Which component of the methodology chapter addresses the demographic analysis and the process of answering the research questions?
- Research Environment.
 - Procedure.
 - Data Processing.**⁷
 - Research Design.
8. Which document in the dissertation research process is designed to present the complete research plan—including research questions, methodology, and the rationale for the study—and is defended before the supervisory committee?
- A. Dissertation Concept Paper.
 - Dissertation Prospectus.**⁸
 - Dissertation Manuscript.
 - Final Dissertation.
9. Which of the following factors contributes significantly to successful dissertation research?
- Strict adherence to established disciplinary boundaries without external collaboration.
 - Reliance solely on pre-existing research findings to avoid risks.

⁷ Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* (YouTube, 2016).

⁸ Sampson, 3.

- Synergy in collaboration combined with good communication, planning, and openness to serendipity.⁹**
- Working in isolation to prevent external influences from diluting the research focus.

10. What is the primary objective of the dissertation manuscript?

- To serve as an internal draft for committee review, with no intention of external dissemination.
- To provide a detailed, exhaustive literature review without addressing the research findings.
- To succinctly present the literature review, research questions, methodology, findings, discussion, and implications with the aim of eventual publication.¹⁰**
- To document only the research method and procedures used in the study.

⁹ Ibid., 10–17.

¹⁰ Sampson, 16.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. YouTube, 2016.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. Euclid University, 2024.
- Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.